

THE NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE ABILITIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Sharipova Makhbuba Bakhshilloevna

Bukhara State University, teacher of the Preschool Education Department,
Doctor of Philosophy in Philology

Shamsiddinova Sarvinoz

Bukhara State University, student of preschool education

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11032329>

Abstract. This article discusses the need and importance of developing creative abilities in preschool education, a creative approach, and the role of creative abilities in modern education.

Keywords: preschool education, future educators, science and education, creativity, professional competence, creative competence, creative potential.

Among the requirements for the field of education, a number of measures have been implemented to increase the professional and creative competence of specialists of preschool educational organizations. The requirement for a teacher is to conduct research on himself first of all. Therefore, the most important need in the preschool education system is the professional maturity of the specialists of the preschool education organization, as well as the creative competence. Creativity (lat., eng. "sreate"-creating, "sreative" creator, creator) expresses the meaning of the creative ability of an individual, which describes the readiness to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor. A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific features, mental sharpness. Also, creativity is reflected as an important factor of talent.

Activities for the development of creative abilities of preschool children play an important role in the formation of a child's personality. All the studies conducted by scientists and psychologists in this field prove that children with creative abilities have a more stable spirit, communicate with them and have a friendly relationship. At a young age, it is recommended to pay special attention to comprehensive development, that is, to the development of literary, artistic and musical abilities of preschool children. The best way to develop creative skills is through play. The purpose of the diagnosis is to determine which type the child is most suitable for and what kind of imagination he has. This can be done with the help of psychologists who conduct special tests, as a result of which games can be

selected to develop the creative abilities of preschool children. It is also possible to independently determine the capabilities of the child, provide him with various activities and observe the most interesting reasons. Determine what kind of imagination has arisen, it is also possible with behavior in the game. If the creative development of babies occurs through the observation and manipulation of objects, the development of more adult children is carried out through attempts to communicate their feelings through the means available to them. Simply put, the tracking phase moves gradually. Methodically offers children's games that develop the creative abilities of preschool children. In particular, there will be classes in the theatrical framework useful for children, because theater activities develop preschoolers in various directions. Children not only learn to complete tasks, participate in theater performances, develop imagination, artistic vision, the ability to perceive the integrity of works, develop the ability to sign. But in this age, the involvement of parents is very important for the development of creative abilities. They should show great interest in the child's activities in the circle and play with him in developing games at home. According to the research of psychologists, by the age of three, all children have approximately the same level of artistic ability. Therefore, wait for the child to show a special talent, and then it is not necessary to develop it. A few simple conditions can be observed each child to develop artistic ability. You need to act at your own pace: at the beginning, to interest the child in drawing, then to show him interest in copying imaginary images, and only after it is clear that he will begin to teach the child the basics of visual arts for deeper reading. Do not forget to support him and, of course, praise and encourage the child's activities. Given the level of development of children, it is necessary to give them additional tasks, to formulate more complex questions. Distracted, quick-tempered, hurried children can be asked to repeat the teacher's instructions and to concentrate before explaining, and to communicate with them in person. For example: "Bahromjon, Nurislam, children, listen carefully, then repeat what I said." This is a very simple and effective method, as it helps to draw children's attention to the teacher's instructions. Therefore, while helping children to remember the task, it also prevents them from responding hastily and thoughtlessly, and helps children to master the task and instructions better. In short, individual work can be done in a small group of children or with a separate child. In order to maintain interest in children's creative work,

individual work is carried out not only with children who have not mastered it, but also with others. Conclusion In addition, individual work has not only educational, developmental, but also educational value when introducing children to certain norms, rules, and so on. We can conclude that a well-organized individual work allows children to fully master the material of the program and has a great positive effect on their behavior

References:

1. Baxshilloevna, S. M. (2022). BOLALAR NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TARBIYACHI NUTQI NAMUNA-O'RNAK VOSITASI SIFATIDA. Scientific Impulse, 1(4), 1288-1292.
2. Baxshilloevna, S. M. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR MA'NAVIY DUNYOSINI BOYITISHDA "ALPOMISH" DOSTONING O'RNI. BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(2), 146-152.
3. Sharipova, M. B. (2021). Laylo Mirzo Qizi Muslimova XALQ DOSTONLARINI O'RGATISHNING AMALIY AHAMIYATI HAMDA DOLZARBLIGI ("ALPOMISH" DOSTONI MISOLIDA). Scientific progress, (7).
4. Sharipova, M. B., & Muslimova, L. M. Q. (2021). XALQ DOSTONLARINI O'RGATISHNING AMALIY AHAMIYATI HAMDA DOLZARBLIGI ("ALPOMISH" DOSTONI MISOLIDA). Scientific progress, 2(7), 1130-1134.
5. Sharipova, M. B. (2021). Xursand Nuriddinovna Mirzayeva XALQIMIZ MADANIYATINING HAYOTBAXSH SARHASHMASI. Scientific progress, (7).
6. Baxshilloevna, S. M. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING NUTQ O'QITISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY AHAMIYATI. PEDAGOGS jurnali, 1(1), 168-168.
7. Baxshulloevna, S. M. (2022). «ALPOMISH» DOSTONI-VATANPARVARLIK FAZILATLARIDAN SABOQ BERUVCHI MA'NAVIY DURDONA. Scientific Impulse, 1(4), 1426-1430.
8. Sharipova, M. B., & Ravshanova, G. F. Q. (2021). QAHRAMONLIK DOSTONLARINING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI: MILLIY RUH VA AN'ANALAR. Scientific progress, 2(7), 1139-1144.
9. Шарипова, М. Б., & Саъдуллаева, М. Б. К. (2020). РАЗВИТИЕ ТВОРЧЕСКИХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ ДЕТЕЙ В ДОШКОЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ. Проблемы педагогики, (6 (51)), 58-60.
10. Sharipova, M. (2020). O'quvchi yoshlar tarbiyasida o'lmas an'ana va marosimlarning ahamiyati. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 1(1).
11. Sharipova, M. B., & Nozirova, M. J. Q. (2021). O'ZBEK XALQ DOSTONLARINI O'QITISHDA KOMPYUTER IMKONIYATLARI. Scientific progress, 2(7), 1102-1108.

12. Sharipova, M. B., & Farmonova, G. S. Q. (2021). NIKOHDAN SO'NG ADO ETILADIGAN URF-ODATLAR TASVIRI ("ALPOMISH" DOSTONI MISOLIDA). Scientific progress, 2(7), 1125-1129.
13. Sharipova, M. B. (2021). XALQ DOSTONLARIDA SOVCHILIK MAROSIMI BADIY IFODASI ("ALPOMISH" DOSTONI MISOLIDA). Scientific progress, 2(7), 1120-1124.
14. Sharipova, M. B., & Mirzayeva, X. N. (2021). XALQIMIZ MADANIYATINING HAYOTBAXSH SARHASHMASI. Scientific progress, 2(7), 1135-1138.
15. Шарипова, М. Б., & Ньматова, Ш. Н. (2020). Формирование эстетической культуры воспитанников дошкольных образовательных учреждений. Вестник магистратуры, (3-3 (102)), 113-114.

